

Relationship between Emotional Intelligence Psychological Adjustment, and Academic Achievement of Public Junior Secondary School Students in Gombe Metropolis, Gombe State

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Abstract

This paper investigated relationship between emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment, and academic achievement of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state. The population consisted of 4,768 students spread across 20 public junior secondary schools in the metropolis. Random sampling was used in sampling four schools out of 20. A total of 236 students were randomly selected from the four schools. A structured research instrument named emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement questionnaire (EIPAA) was used in collecting data. A split half method was used in establishing the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.720 was obtained. Frequencies, percentages, Pearson product moment correlation and t test were used in analysing the data collected. The study finds out that 70% percent of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis are emotionally intelligent while 30% are not. 73% of the students are found to be psychologically adjusted while 27% are not. The study also finds out that there is strong relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological adjustment of junior secondary school students. There is no insignificant relationship between emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis. The study recommended that students should be help to develop the ability to understand feelings in the right manner both in oneself and others. They should also be thought methods to employ for keeping and restoring harmony between themselves and their environment for proper adjustment. Focus should be on other non-cognitive factors that affects academic achievement of students.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment, academic achievement, junior secondary school students*

Introduction

In the lives of most young people, the schools probably second only to the home as a basic influence in the feelings a person will acquire with regard to himself and others. In some respect the school influence is more important than that of the home, for life at school includes areas of experience that are outside the reach of home. When a child goes to the school, he enters a world that is removed from the protection that is accorded to him at home. He is put upon his own. He is placed in the hands of strange adults a new parental figure- at an age when he still needs adult support. The child is thrown into dealing with his peers during a phase of his development when social relationships with his age group are becoming very important to him. The attitudes others show towards him and the judgement they place upon him will have an important bearing upon his growing conception of himself (Skinner, 2009). Emotional development pattern plays an important in the personal and social development of an individual. An individual with stable emotional pattern leads a happy, healthy and peaceful life. He is at ease with himself and his surroundings. On the other hand, an individual who is emotionally disturbed becomes a problem for himself as well as for others. Continues emotional disturbance affects the individual's growth and development. Therefore, the development of emotions is extremely important for the harmonious development of the personality of an individual. Emotions influence all the aspect of an individual's personality. Proper training and education will go a long way to enable the young people to control their emotions and obtain a mental balance and stability (Aggarwal, 2011).

According to Mangal (2011) an emotionally adjusted individual is the one that demonstrate the following traits and characteristics in his behaviour:

- I. Almost all the emotions are seen in him and their patterns of expressions can be easily recognised
- II. Usually, the person expresses his emotions in a socially acceptable way
- III. The person is able to exercise control over his emotions
- IV. The person perceives things in real perspective
- V. The person is guided by his intellect rather than his emotions.

- VI. He never argues in defence of his undesirable improper conduct. He also never shifts the responsibility of his mistakes to others. Thus, he is always honest.
- VII. He possesses adequate self-respect and self- concept.
- VIII. He is not confined to himself. He thinks about others and is keen to maintain social relations.
- IX. He can exercise his emotions at a proper time in a proper place

Historically speaking, the term emotional intelligence was introduced in 1990 by two American university professors Mayer and Salovey (2004) in their attempt to develop a scientific measure of knowing the differences in people's ability to in the area of emotions. They defined emotional intelligence as the capacity of to reason with emotions in four areas: to perceive emotions, to integrate it in thought, to understand it and to manage its

In addition, positive psychology studies have increased in recent years especially the eighties of the last century. Therefore, Studies paid more attention to Emotional Intelligence since it is one of the variables of positive preventive psychology for utilizing the positive side of emotions and feelings in addressing many issues of concern to the individual, family and society. It also means the potential exploitation of both emotion and intelligence for the human mental health and to achieve the quality of psychological adjustment. Emotional Intelligence according to the Bar-On model of emotional-social intelligence is defined as "a cross-section of interrelated emotional and social competencies, skills and facilitators that determine how effectively we understand and express ourselves, understand others and relate with them, and cope with daily demands (Rizkallah, 2006, p. 61). Rather than just a cognitive ability, emotional intelligence it is shown as a set of emotion-related self-perceptions, referring to one's competence to use, understand, and regulate emotions, and such perceptions are linked to other psychological constructs such as personality traits, motivational, or social factors (Qualter et al, 2011). Emotional intelligence, which is essential for the good processing and managing of emotional information, can be regarded as a psychological resource (Di Fabio & Saklofske, 2014). According to the scientific literature, emotional intelligence promotes the psychological well-being, adjustment, and mental health of students as it provides them with the necessary skills to deal with daily challenging situations (Fernández-Berrocal & Extremera, 2016).

On the other hand, adjustment is considered one of the basic concepts in mental health, since most of the behaviours of the individual whether successful or unsuccessful are just attempts to adjustment in order to reduce the tension suffered by the individual. Sound psychological adjustment paves for the principle of self-control, social moderation, flexibility and adaptability to the individuals in the community. Cetinkaya-Yeldizet et al (2011) are of the opinion that psychological adjustment focuses on psychological well-being, satisfaction and interactive components of the host environment. Sufian (2004) defines it as the individual's satisfaction of his psychological needs, self-acceptance, enjoyment of tension-free life, free of conflicts and psychological disorders, enjoyment of intimate social relations, participation in social activities, and acceptance of the customs, traditions and values of society. Psychological adjustment involves personal and emotional adjustment, social adjustment, Family Adjustment, and School Adjustment. Another definition is that given by Mangal (2011) opined that it is the interaction between a person and environment. How one adjusts in a particular situation depends upon one's personal characteristics as also the circumstances of the situation. In other words, both personal and environmental factors work side by side in adjustment. An individual is adjusted if he is adjusted to himself and to his environment.

Studies that were conducted on the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and psychological adjustment revealed strong relationship, one of such study was that of study Tasnim et al (2019) who conducted a study on psychological adjustment and academic achievement of adolescent. The study finds out that there is direct and significant relationship between psychological adjustment and academic achievement. Respondent from higher psychological adjustment group were higher in academic achievement than those from poor psychological. So also, respondent from medium psychological adjustment had higher academic achievement than those from lower psychological adjustment. Baron (2000) who aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a training program of Emotional Intelligence on the adjustment of university students. The results of the study revealed that there is a great relationship between Emotional Intelligence and adjustment among female students. Alabboushi (2009) investigated the effect of an educational program based on Goleman emotional intelligence theory on improving social adjustment and achievement among a sample of students with learning difficulties in Jordan. The results of the study showed statistically significant differences between the experimental group and the control group on the social adjustment scale in favour of the experimental group, while there was no statistically significant difference on the academic achievement variable.

Aldiasty (2010) conducted a study about the Emotional Intelligence and its relationship to psychosocial and social adjustment among a sample of children (13-16 years). The study concluded that the high level of Emotional Intelligence gives an individual psychosocial and social adjustment with social, family, or school situations. Albalwy (2004) conducted a study to identify the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and psychological adjustment and social skills among a sample of female students in the Faculty of Education in Tabuk. The study sample consisted of (290) students. The findings of the study revealed that there was a statistically significant positive relationship between the scores of students on the Emotional Intelligence scale dimensions and their scores on the Psychological Adjustment Scale. Such studies drew attention to the importance of the role of Emotional Intelligence in the academic achievement and in achieving psychological adjustment of the individual. Emotional Intelligence now is of as great importance as mental intelligence, since it enables the individual to be more adjusted with him/herself. It serves as the bridge that leads to success in various fields of life.

A study by Asmari (2014) investigated the effect of emotional intelligence of academic performance of Jaipur (India) senior secondary school students on a sample of 1000 students drawn using random - cum cluster sampling technique using the survey method of data collection. The study revealed a positive effect of emotional intelligence on academic achievement of the students especially the girl child. A study by Mervat (2016) who investigated relationship between emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic performance among adolescents found out significant relationship between the variables of emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement among normal female students.

This study intends to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic performance of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.

Objectives

1. To find out the level of Emotional Intelligence among junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.
- 2 To find out the level of psychological adjustment of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.

3. To determine whether there is relationship between Emotional Intelligence and psychological adjustment among public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.
4. To find out whether there is gender difference in the emotional and psychological adjustment of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.
5. To determine the relationship between emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.

Research questions

1. What is the level of Emotional Intelligence of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state?
2. What is the level of psychological adjustment of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state?

Research hypotheses

1. There is no relationship between Emotional Intelligence and psychological adjustment of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.
2. There is no gender difference in the emotional and psychological adjustment of public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was made up of all public junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state. This consisted of 4,768 students spread across 20 junior secondary schools in the metropolis. Random sampling was used in sampling four schools out of 20. A total of 236 students were randomly selected from the four schools. The sample consisted of male and female JSS one student with age range between 11- 16 years. A structured research instrument named Emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment questionnaire and academic achievement (EIPAA) was used in collecting data. The questionnaire was a closed ended and used the Likert response scale type. It has 5 options, that is strongly agree, agree, undecided, strongly disagree and disagree. It consisted of 3 sections: section 1 is on personal information, section 2 on emotional intelligence and section 3 is on psychological adjustment. A face validity of the instrument was sought through giving the instruments to two experts in educational psychology to

validate the instrument. A split half method was used in establishing the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.720 was obtained. The instrument was administered with the help of research assistants. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentages to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics of t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used in testing the hypothesis 3,4 and 5.

Results:

Research question one: What is the level of Emotional Intelligence of JSS 1 secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state?

Table 1: Analysis of student’s responses in frequencies and percentages

s/n	Statements	SA		A		U		SD		D	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	I have good sense of my feelings most of the time	159	67.1	64	27.0	4	1.7	7	3.0	2	.8
2	I really understand what I feel	104	43.9	65	27.4	22	9.3	21	8.9	24	10.1
3	I always know whether I am happy or not	43	18.1	36	15.2	30	12.7	76	32.1	51	21.5
4	I know my friend’s behaviour and emotions	77	32.5	127	53.6	17	7.2	10	4.2	5	2.1
5	I am a good observer of other’s emotions	94	39.7	52	22.9	35	14.8	31	13.1	24	10.1
6	I am sensitive to the feelings and other’s emotions	100	42.2	81	34.2	21	8.9	14	5.9	20	8.4
7	I have good understanding of the emotions of people around me	124	52.3	53	22.4	19	8.0	21	8.9	19	8.0
8	I always set goals for myself and work	119	50.2	74	31.2	21	8.9	12	5.1	10	4.2

	towards achieving them										
9	I always tell myself what a competent person I am	81	34.2	73	30.8	22	9.3	27	11.4	33	13.9
10	I always use alternative actions in some situations	83	35.0	64	27.0	37	15.6	28	11.8	24	10.1
11	I incorporate my own and other people's emotions in decision making	80	33.8	78	32.9	32	13.5	25	10.5	20	8.4
12	I am able to control my temper so I can handle difficulties rationally	101	42.6	64	27.0	28	11.8	19	8.0	23	9.7
13	I am quite capable of controlling my emotions	94	39.7	52	21.9	22	9.3	42	17.7	26	11.0

Summary of the table:

Response type	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree/agree	165	70%
Undecided	24	10.0%
Strongly disagree/disagree	47	20%
Total	236	100%

The summary of table 1 indicated that 165 respondents representing 70% agree which the statements on emotional intelligence while 24 of the respondents representing 10% were undecided and 47 respondents representing 20% of the respondents disagree. This shows that the level of agreement with the items has passed the level of disagreement, which means that most of the students are emotionally intelligent thus can adjust well emotionally in new environment.

Table 2: Research question 2: What is the level of psychological adjustment of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state?

SN	Statements	SA		A		U		SD		D	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	I am successfully doing my best in school	152	64.1	55	23.2	15	6.3	10	4.2	4	1.7
2	I always follow instructions	152	64.1	55	23.2	15	6.3	10	4.2	4	1.7
3	I always organize and plan my activities	128	54.0	74	31.2	14	5.9	9	3.8	11	4.6
4	I always want to be the centre of attention	94	39.7	69	29.1	24	10.1	28	11.9	21	8.9
5	I always like to accept responsibilities	101	42.6	53	22.4	14	5.9	32	13.5	36	15.2
6	I am loyal to my friends and have strong attachment	113	47.7	71	30.0	16	6.8	22	9.3	14	5.9
7	I do analyse the behaviour and feelings of others	96	40.5	62	26.2	26	11.1	36	15.2	16	6.8
8	I do seek encouragement and aid from others	110	40.5	80	33.8	17	7.2	13	5.5	16	6.8
9	I always want to be a leader and influence others to follow me	87	36.7	54	22.8	26	11.0	34	14.3	35	14.8
10	I do accept blame and confess errors to others	104	43.9	65	27.4	28	11.8	20	8.4	19	8.0
11	I sympathise with my classmates and assist them	136	57.4	68	28.7	15	6.3	12	5.1	5	2.1
12	I seek new experience and avoid routine	118	49.8	73	30.8	23	9.7	14	5.9	8	3.4
13	I do follow task through to the end	120	50.6	79	33.3	12	5.1	14	5.9	11	4.6
14	I want to be attractive and associate with the opposite sex	51	21.5	47	19.8	29	12.2	51	21.5	58	24.5
15	I want to express myself and not be critical of others	97	40.9	62	26.2	15	6.3	26	11.0	36	15.2

Summary of the table

Response type	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree/agree	174	73%
Undecided	21	09%
Strongly disagree/disagree	41	18%
Total	236	100%

The summary of table 2 indicated that 174 respondents representing 73% agree which the statements on psychological adjustment while 21 of the respondents representing 9% were undecided and 41 respondents representing 18% of the respondents disagree. This shows that the level of agreement has passed the level of disagreement, which means that most of the students were psychologically adjusted within the new environment.

Table 3: Research Hypothesis 1: there is no relationship between Emotional Intelligence and psychological adjustment of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state?

Variable	N	df	R	P value	sg
Emotional intelligence	13	26	.833	0.374	0.05
Psychological adjustment	15				

Table 3 shows that the r stands at 0.833 while the P value of r stands at 0.374 at 0.05 level of significance, this shows that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological adjustment of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state.

Table 4: Research Hypothesis 2: there is no gender difference in the emotional and psychological adjustment of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state?

variable	N	Df	Mean	t	P	sig
male	98	234	4.33	.124	1.9719	0.05
female	138		4.31			

Table 4 shows that the t of .124 is less than the P value of t which is 1.9719 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significance gender difference in the emotional intelligence and psychological adjustment of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that 70% to 73% of junior secondary school students are emotionally intelligent and psychologically adjusted while 30% of them are not. The reason might be that majority of the JSS 1 students migrate from the primary school to junior secondary school of the same school. This is in line with Mangal (2011) who opined that it is the interaction between a person and environment. How one adjusts in a particular situation depends upon one's personal characteristics as also the circumstances of the situation. In other words, both personal and environmental factors work side by side in adjustment. An individual is adjusted if he is adjusted to himself and to his environment. The finding also is in line with that of Aldiasty (2010) who conducted a study about the Emotional Intelligence and its relationship to psychosocial and social adjustment among a sample of children (13-16 years). The study concluded that the high level of Emotional Intelligence gives an individual psychosocial and social adjustment with social, family, or school situations.

The finding of the study also revealed that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological adjustment. This is in agreement with the finding of Albalwy (2004) conducted a study to identify the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and psychological adjustment and social skills among a sample of female students in the Faculty of Education in Tabuk. The study sample consisted of (290) students. The findings of the study revealed that there was a statistically significant positive relationship between the scores of students on the Emotional Intelligence scale dimensions and their scores on the Psychological Adjustment Scale.

The study finds out that there is no significance gender difference in the emotional intelligence and psychological adjustment of junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis of Gombe state. This is not in agreement with Abzakh (2010) who investigated the effect of an educational program based on Goleman Emotional Intelligence Theory on improving social adjustment and achievement among a sample of students with learning difficulties in Jordan. The results of the study showed statistically significant differences between the experimental group and the control group on the social

adjustment scale in favour of the experimental group, while there was no statistically significant difference on the academic achievement variable.

The finding of the study that there is no relationship between emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement among public junior secondary school students in Gombe state disagrees with Mervat (2016) who investigated relationship between emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic performance among adolescents found out significant relationship between the variables of emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement among normal female students. This difference may be as a result of different geographical location of the two studies

Conclusion

The finding of the study revealed that most of the junior secondary school students in Gombe metropolis are emotionally intelligent and psychologically adjusted only about 27 -30% were found wanting. There is also a strong correlation between emotional intelligence and psychological adjustment. It is only when one is emotionally intelligent that he can adjust well in any environment that he finds himself. However, there was insignificant relationship among the three variables of emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement. Thus, an emotionally adjusted individual and a psychologically adjusted will have better academic achievement.

Recommendations

1. Parents, family members and teachers support will greatly help students in maintaining their emotional intelligence, psychological adjustment and academic achievement. .
2. Teachers should take time and effort to develop not only the cognitive professional skills but also the effective skills for the development of emotional intelligence.
3. Designing activities for the students that have been found wanting to help them develop their emotional intelligence and adjust well to their psychological environment.
4. Focus should be on other non-cognitive factors that affects academic achievement. As the variables of the study have not shown significant relationship among one another.

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